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Enhancement of Proton Density Magnetic Resonance Images using Histogram Equalization and Unsharp Masking

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Abstract

Objective: The main objective of this study is to enhance the contrast and edge information present in the Proton density magnetic resonance medical images to increase the perception of information and provide better visualization format for effective diagnostics and treatment. **Method:** In the proposed algorithm, adaptive histogram equalization is applied to the input proton density magnetic resonance image to enhance the contrast followed by the unsharp mask filtering to improve the high frequency edge information of the image. Four proton density magnetic resonance images were downloaded from the dataset available in National Library of Medicine website, the experiment was carried out by writing the MATLAB code and executed by Intel Pentium Processor CPU4417U @ 2.3 GHz. **Findings:** Results reveal that the proposed method out performs adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) technique and Classical Unsharp Masking Filter (CUMF) both in terms of visual quality along with edge preservation and contrast enhancement. The quality of output image from the proposed method is enhanced by 1.34 times over AHE & 1.88 times over CUMF in terms of Spatial Frequency and 1.33 times over AHE & 2.18 times over CUMF in terms of Sharpness. **Novelty:** This study combines both histogram equalization and unsharp masking to enhance both contrast and edge information of proton density magnetic resonance medical images for effective diagnostics and treatment.

Keywords: Proton Density Magnetic Resonance Images; Medical Image Enhancement; Unsharp Mask Filter; Histogram Equalization; Spatial Frequency; Mean Gradient; Sharpness

1 Introduction

Proton Density Magnetic Resonance Images (PD-MRI) should consist of contrast and edge information about various parts of our body needed by Physician for diagnostic and treatment purpose. The sensors used in Magnetic Resonance imaging system may blur the image to some degree resulting low contrast which reduces the visual quality of

the image. To increase the perceived quality of the PD-MRI images, edge information must be enhanced along with the contrast of the image. Global Histogram Equalization (GHE) is the most popular and widely used spatial domain image enhancement method to enhance the contrast of images taken by different imaging modalities. GHE method flattens the Probability Distribution Function (PDF) and improves contrast of an input image by stretching the dynamic range of gray levels from 0 to 255. Since it utilizes the cumulative density function (CDF) to enhance the gray levels of input image⁽¹⁾, the local contrast of an image is not improved. It varies mean brightness level of an input image and causes intensity saturation and over enhancement of image. The efficient technique to limit the level of enhancement in GHE method was proposed by Y.T. Kim and this method is called as like Brightness Preserving Bi Histogram Equalization (BBHE)⁽²⁾. To preserve the mean brightness while enhancing the contrast of input image, BBHE divides the input image histogram into two sub histograms based on the mean brightness, and both sub histograms are equalized independently. To preserve brightness along with average information content of the image, another technique called as, Dualistic Sub Image Histogram Equalization (DSIHE) was proposed by Wang et. al. which incorporates segmentation based on the median value⁽³⁾. To overcome the problem of over enhancement in DSIHE method, another technique called as Recursive Mean Separate Histogram Equalization (RMSHE) was proposed by S.D. Chen and A.R. Ramali⁽⁴⁾. RMSHE method uses mean based threshold for segmentation. Adaptive histogram equalization (AHE) is another method of histogram equalization for enhancing the contrast of the image that computes several histograms, each corresponds to a distinct window of an image. AHE over amplifies the artifacts in homogeneous regions of the image. A variant of AHE called Contrast Limited AHE (CLAHE) prevents this drawback by limiting the contrast amplification⁽⁵⁾. In literature, huge amount of histogram equalization based contrast enhancement techniques are available to solve the problem of mean brightness shifting and all the histogram equalization methods enhance the contrast of the image but fail to preserve the high frequency information. At the same time, the Classical Unsharp Mask Filter⁽⁶⁾ (CUMF) and its different variants attract more attention from the researchers due to its simplicity in enhancing the high frequency edge information of various types of images. CUMF enhances the edge information but fails to enhance the contrast of the images. To overcome the limitation of both histogram equalization based techniques and CUMF, this study proposes a new approach to enhance the contrast and high frequency information like edges of low contrast PD-MRI images by combining CLAHE and CUMF. The proposed method provides satisfying results over GHE, BBHE, DSIHE, RMSHE, CLAHE and CUMF in terms of spatial frequency, mean gradient, entropy and sharpness. The following section presents the enhancement methodology. Section 3 discusses the performance of the proposed method. Finally, summary of this study with conclusion is presented.

2 Methodology

Adaptive histogram equalization and its variants are well-known contrast enhancement methods for all modalities of images ranging from satellite images to medical images. Similarly, Unsharp masking filter is well known for its simplicity and effectiveness in enhancing the sharpness of the images. This study combines CLAHE and CUMF to enhance the contrast and edge information of low contrast PD-MRI images simultaneously.

2.1 Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization

Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) is one of the most popular and acceptable variant of histogram equalization based contrast enhancement of digital images. This method is implemented by dividing the image into several non-overlapping regions of equal sizes called windows, resulting three regions namely Corner Region, Border Region and Inner Region. At first step, the histogram of each region is calculated. Then based on the clip limited defined by the user for contrast expansion, modified histogram is obtained in which the height of the histogram does not go beyond the clip limit. Finally, CDF of the modified contrast limited histograms are determined for gray scale mapping. In CLAHE method, pixels are mapped linearly by combining the results from the mapping of four nearest regions. Formulation of this approach for Inner Regions is straight forward. However, for regions in Corner Region and Border Region groups, this formulation requires some special consideration. The Figure 1 shows the comparison of contrast enhancement of an image along with the histogram by GHE and CLAHE.

2.2 Classical Unsharp Masking Filter

CUMF is widely used to sharpen the all type of images and its name originates from the fact that CUMF enhances high frequency information like edges and fine details. Figure 2 shows the structure of CUMF. It enhances the images through a process which subtracts the blurred version of an image from the original image to get the high frequency information. To generate the blurred

version, normally Gaussian or box filter is used. The UMF can be computed using the following equation,

$$U(x, y) = I(x, y) + \gamma * [I(x, y) - G(x, y)]$$

where $U(x, y)$ is the sharpened output image, $I(x, y)$ is the original input image, $G(x, y)$ is blurred version of Input image $I(x, y)$ which is filtered by a low-pass Gaussian filter. γ is a scaling constant, whose larger values increase the amounts of the produced sharpness.

Fig 1. Comparison of Contrast Enhancement by GHE and CLAHE

Fig 2. Classical Unsharp Masking Filter

2.3 Procedure

This study enhances the medical images and presents in a better visualization format to do medical analysis. This is achieved by enhancing the contrast and increasing visual quality of high frequency edge information of medical images. The proposed methodology to enhance the contrast and edge information is shown in Figure 3. The proposed methodology receives the low contrast image as input and passes through the classical UMF. For implementing CUMF, this paper uses “imsharpen” in MATLAB. The scaling constant value γ is set to 0.8. The output from the classical UMF is the edge enhanced medical image and it is passed through contrast limited AHE. For AHE, the window size is set as 8X8 and the clip limit is set as 0.01 to avoid the over enhancement of contrast. The function called “adapthiseq” in MATLAB is used to implement CLAHE. The output from CLAHE is edge and contrast improved image.

Fig 3. Proposed Methodology

3 Results and Discussion

Experimental evaluations and results are provided in this section to find out the strength of our proposed methodology in enhancing the medical images. The image enhancement based on Global Histogram Equalization (GHE), Brightness preserving Bi Histogram Equalization (BBHE), Dualistic Sub Image Histogram Equalization (DSIHE), Recursive Mean Separate Histogram Equalization (RMSHE), Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE), Classical UMF (CUMF) and the proposed method was implemented using MATLAB simulation package. Four proton density weighted magnetic resonance images (namely Thorax, Abdomen, Pelvis and Thigh) were downloaded from the dataset available in National Library of Medicine website, the experiment were carried out on these images by writing the MATLAB code and executed by Intel Pentium Processor CPU4417U @ 2.3 GHz. The main objective of this study is to enhance both contrast and edge information present in the Proton density magnetic resonance medical images. The enhanced image should be evaluated qualitatively using visual display and quantitatively using image quality metrics. The image quality metrics considered for quantitative analysis are Spatial Frequency (SF), Mean Gradient, Entropy and sharpness⁽⁷⁻¹⁰⁾. These values are tabulated in Table 1 and visual quality results of Medical Image enhancement are shown in Figure 4.

Table 1. Results of Medical Image Enhancement

Image	Thorax Image							
Method	Original	HE	BBHE	DSIHE	RMSHE	AHE	CUMF	Proposed
SF	15.3905	33.3761	37.2352	34.3015	35.8584	34.1954	22.5162	47.2976
Gradient	10.3543	25.4241	25.6615	25.5831	21.4141	24.6603	15.2805	34.857
Entropy	6.5811	5.561	6.3478	6.464	5.9229	7.3491	6.6932	7.3693
Sharpness	8.2756	18.5795	19.6583	19.1702	17.2797	19.2232	11.4709	25.548
Image	Abdomen Image							
SF	19.1055	44.106	49.3994	44.9352	52.1819	41.5794	28.0799	56.0352
Gradient	13.0478	29.0542	31.2372	29.537	31.9149	29.7481	19.3497	41.0128
Entropy	6.9227	5.8903	6.743	6.8124	6.4185	7.7364	7.0151	7.7621
Sharpness	10.446	23.1873	24.9047	23.6056	25.3095	23.5424	14.5273	30.4978
Image	Pelvis Image							
SF	16.807	33.4107	36.9879	35.0125	37.9431	32.7635	24.2375	44.4145
Gradient	9.727	20.3111	21.3824	21.3051	20.9011	21.1661	14.2861	29.6185
Entropy	6.7442	5.7222	6.5094	6.5448	6.1287	7.4108	6.8069	7.4511
Sharpness	7.8652	15.9122	16.8956	16.698	16.8492	16.7658	10.8217	22.0763
Image	Thigh Image							
SF	18.6035	33.1502	34.4288	36.0675	33.5548	30.6707	25.8226	40.5658
Gradient	9.7279	22.5844	21.5624	23.2595	16.1691	18.8346	13.7889	25.7084
Entropy	6.2071	5.1479	5.9469	6.0073	5.3873	6.788	6.268	6.8172
Sharpness	7.8932	16.2652	16.2741	17.3748	13.2776	14.7728	10.4691	19.0004

In Figure 4, the four input images are shown in row 1. The enhanced images using GHE, BBHE, DSIHE, RMSHE, CLAHE and CUMF method is shown from row 2 to row 7 respectively. From the results, it can be observed that visual quality of the resultant images are not up to the mark. Over brightness is resulted in GHE method. The resultant image of CLAHE method is visually looking good but lacks in edge information. The CUMF enhances the edge information in the output image but fails to enhance the contrast of the images. The output image of the proposed method is displayed in row 8 of Figure 4. In that image, both contrast and edge information is present and looks so good. The quantitative analysis of the proposed method in comparison with various enhancement methods is done with the help of image quality metrics Spatial Frequency, Mean Gradient, Entropy and sharpness. Spatial Frequency and Entropy provide the level of clarity whereas Mean Gradient and sharpness provide the edge information. From the table, it is inferred that proposed method enhances both contrast and edge information of PD-MRI image. GHE increases the overall contrast of the input image, but the local contrast of an image is not improved since it stretches the dynamic range of gray levels from 0 to 255. BBHE slightly controls the improvement in brightness and increases the local contrast by dividing the input image histogram into two sub histograms based on the mean brightness, and both sub histograms are equalized independently. The brightness along with average information content of the image is preserved by DSIHE by segmenting the input image histogram based on the median value. Contrast Limited AHE limits the contrast

amplification and maintains balance between local and global contrast of the input image. All histogram equalization methods enhance the contrast of the image but fail to preserve the high frequency information. CUMF enhances the high frequency edge information of input image but the contrast of the input image is maintained. The proposed method takes the advantage from CLAHE and CUMF enhances both the contrast & high frequency edge information of input image which is clearly evident from the images shown in row8 of Figure 4.

Fig 4. Results of Medical Image Enhancement

4 Conclusion

In this study, a novel method of medical image enhancement by combining adaptive histogram equalization and classical Unsharp masking filter is introduced. First, each input image is filtered using CUMF to enhance the edge information. Then, this edge enhanced image is filtered using CLHCE to enhance the contrast. As a result, the proposed methodology tremendously improves the edge information and enhances the contrast of PD-MRI images to do effective medical analysis. The proposed method is compared Histogram Equalization methods such as GHE, BBHE, DISHE, RMSHE, AHE and classical UMF. From the results, it is inferred that the histogram based methods improve the contrast but fail to enhance the edge details. The classical UMF enhances the high frequency edge information but fails to improve the contrast of PD-MRI images. The proposed method enhances both contrast and edge details of PD-MRI Images. Furthermore, the accuracy of the obtained results is measured quantitatively using four well-known metrics like SF, Mean Gradient, Entropy and Sharpness. From the obtained results, it is well proven that the proposed method of enhancement by combining adaptive histogram equalization and classical Unsharp masking filter provided satisfying results and outperformed the CLAHE and CUMF in terms of qualitative and quantitative assessment. The quality of output image from the proposed method is enhanced by 1.34 times over AHE & 1.88 times over CUMF in terms of Spatial Frequency, 1.39 times over AHE & 2.13 times over CUMF in terms of Gradient and 1.33 times over AHE & 2.18 times over CUMF in terms of Sharpness. There is small increase in entropy from 7.321075 and 6.6958 to 7.349925

for the proposed method over AHE and CUMF. Even though experiments are demonstrated for PD-MRI images, proposed algorithm can also be applied on other medical imaging modalities as well.

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